

EFFECT OF AU ION IRRADIATION ON SILICON CARBIDE COMPOSITES

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SiC_f/SiC composites are being studied for years for nuclear applications such as structural components in fusion reactors [1-2], or cladding in some fission reactors of Generation IV such as HTR or GFR [3]. Recently, it has also been suggested for hexagonal wrapper in SFR [4] and pin fuel in water reactors [5]. The main advantages brought by the use of this material (low density, low activation, neutron transparency, chemical stability, low swelling) combined with crosscutting issues lead to significant advances both from the fundamental point of view and the technological aspect. In particular, behavior under irradiation of SiC_f/SiC is investigated through many neutron irradiation experiments in reactors [6]. This allowed, for instance, to assess stability of SiC_f/SiC manufactured with well crystallized and stoichiometric fibers of third generation (Tyranno SA3, Hi-Nicalon-S), to highlight dramatic drop in thermal conductivity, to address the importance of the interface material [7], etc. In parallel, stability under irradiation of bulk SiC is also widely investigated both by neutrons irradiation and ion implantation in fundamental understanding purposes [8]. Because of the heterogeneous structure of the SiC_f/SiC, charged particles irradiations are barely used for basic researches [9]. However, it should be a useful tool to assess new materials, for instance with upgraded interfaces or innovative matrix, before launching dedicated neutron irradiation experiments. This sounds also consistent with the wide working conditions presently envisaged for SiC_f/SiC materials (temperature, neutron energy, and environment).

In this work, three SiC_f/SiC grades involving the same Chemical Vapor Infiltrated (CVI) SiC matrix but various types of fibers were irradiated with 12

MeV Au ions up to 0.05 and 1 dpa both at room temperature (RT) and 800°C. Microstructure examination and Raman spectroscopy are presented to highlight the behavior of Tyranno S (TS), Tyranno SA3 (TSA3) and Hi-Nicalon type S (HNS) fibers within the SiC matrix.

After irradiation statistical analyses were performed in prior chosen bundles to evidence potential differences of behavior between fibers and matrix, e. g. in terms of swelling. No significant changes could be detected neither in diameter (average diameter 9.9 μm) nor shape factor (average shape factor of 0.91), as shown in Fig.1.

Then, scanning electron microscope observations were conducted at the fiber scale. Step height differences among the SiC matrix, the PyC interface and the TS fibers were observed for the irradiated composites for 1 dpa dose at RT and 800 °C. This step height is quantitatively evaluated through AFM measurements. Fig. 2 shows 3D-AFM images of RT (1 dpa) irradiated TS SiC_f/SiC composites in "contact mode". The profile analysis along a fiber (see Fig. 2c) shows that the height step is ~350 nm at RT. Damaged materials were investigated by transmission electron microscopy along the beam penetration. Damages are mainly located at amorphous zones in the matrix, as well as in the fiber themselves. TS fiber shrinkage together with slight expansion of the matrix was already observed for ion irradiation at room temperature, related to full amorphization at a dose of about 1 dpa. The formation of such amorphous layer is consistent with Raman microspectrometry results. However, this effect is enhanced by a decreased swelling of β-SiC matrix at higher irradiation temperature (800 °C)

suggesting irradiation defect annealing, which is consistent with Raman data that show a slightly disordered material with increasing temperature. In contrast, this type of morphology change is not observed for TSA3 and HNS composites irradiated under the same conditions.

Fig. 1. Distribution in diameter of the 1580 TS fibers: (a) before and (b) after irradiation at RT up to 1dpa. Average diameter is ~9.9 μm in both cases.

Fig. 2. 3D-AFM images of the TS composite samples irradiated at 1 dpa fluence (a) at RT and (b) at 800 °C. (c) and (d) Profile analysis along the line indicated respectively in (a) and (b)

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